

Predictors of Job-Hopping Intention and Academics' Engagement in Southwest Nigeria: A Moderating Role of Generational Diversity

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Abstract

Many universities worldwide have lost a sizable portion of their critical faculty regarding physical removal, work engagement, and loyalty, reducing involvement in their fundamental tasks (research production, teaching engagement, and community service engagement). In this study, we explored the moderating role of generational diversity on academic attention and the desire to change jobs. The job embeddedness theory serves as the study's theoretical foundation. A five-point Likert scale questionnaire surveyed 620 academics from a few universities in Southwest Nigeria. The respondents were chosen for this study using a convenience random sampling method. Five hundred and forty-five copies of the questionnaire, or an 87.9% response rate, were returned and used in the analysis. The moderating impact of generational diversity on the perceived link between predictors of the desire to change jobs and academic engagement was assessed using structural equation modelling (SEM). The results demonstrate that indicators of exogenous factors (predictors of job-hopping intention and generational diversity) accounted for 62.7% of the variability in academics' involvement in the chosen universities. Generational diversity's moderating effects, however, were determined to be insignificant. Consequently, generational variation has to predict the impact on academic involvement. Therefore, the study recommends that the university's management should promote diversity management by harnessing the inherent benefits of diversity to enhance academic engagement. Also, to foster generational synergy in the workplace, management must understand the variations among generational cohorts.

Keywords: Generational diversity, Job hopping intention, Academic engagement

Introduction

Background to the Study

Globally, the movement of employees from one organisation to another has made employee engagement a burning topic of discussion in recent years. The worst scenario is when the desirable ones voluntarily disengage from their current employment and join other organisations (Kundu & Lata 2017). An individual who often changes his or her job is described as job-hopping (Pranaya 2014). Cited by Yuen (2016), the definition of job-hopping is an individual leaving his or her employers to enhance his or her career and increase his or her professional development and growth.

Historically, it was common for employees to have a lifelong career at one or two organisations while progressing vertically throughout that same organisation. In contrast to the definition of corporate loyalty in the past, the desire for lifetime employment is fading away, and the current focus is "job-hopping" anywhere across the globe (Mohammed, 2015; Sharjeel & Beenish, 2017). Upon examining this paradigm shift in employees' psychological contracts, Kelly and Marie-Anne (2016) reported that employees now move from one organisation to another in pursuit of better pay and career development. The desire for lifetime employment is fading, and the current focus is "job-hopping" anywhere globally (Mohammed, 2015; Sharjeel & Beenish, 2017).

Job-hopping is emerging as a significant challenge for many organisations nowadays. Recent studies on the job-hopping phenomenon point to three generations currently dominating the workforce. These generations are Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Generation Y (Becton, Walker & Jones-Farmer, 2014; Kelly & Marie-Anne, 2016; Niki, 2017). The word generation refers to a body of individuals born and living simultaneously who share common values and characteristics, resulting from certain significant events in their formative years (Kelly & Marie-Anne, 2016). The unique experiences introduced during their formative years contribute to the values of the individuals in the generational cohort (Niki, 2017). These generational differences are prevalent in the working environment as almost every company will employ individuals from different generations. The young generation has been reported to tend to change jobs more frequently due to their low loyalty to employers (Yuen, 2016). However, there is a lack of consistent views on whether job-hopping behaviour differs from generation to generation (Twenge, 2010; Kelly & Marie-Anne, 2016).

Also, extant literature reveals that job-hopping phenomenon could be found in different generations and organisations (Refilwe, 2014; Mensah, Luther & Appiagyei, 2015). Studies such as Akpa, et al. (2016), Yuen (2016), and Demetria (2018) indicated that job-hopping phenomenon seems to be shared among academic staff of higher institutions. Lack of job growth opportunities, leadership problems, co-workers not being treated well, and being passed over for promotion are reasons for the high rate of job-hopping among academics.

As such, their engagement has been reported to be declining as academics' mobility increases (Demetria, 2018). Akpa, et al. (2016) argued that many universities around the world, both public and

private, have lost significant numbers of their critical faculty, not only in terms of their physical removal but in their work engagement and loyalty, thus reducing involvement in their core responsibilities (research output, teaching engagement, and community service engagement). This imposes a severe barrier to achieving the desired objectives of many universities.

Although a considerable body of research has been done globally on the correlation between Job-hopping intention and employee engagement (Mustapha & Zakaria, 2013; Thanuja, Ng Siew & Keng Kok. 2016), it is interesting to note that hardly any study addressed the moderating role of generational diversity on the relationship between job-hopping intentions and academics' engagement. Against this background, this study intended to establish the perceived moderating role of generational diversity on the relationship between job-hopping intention and academic engagement among selected universities in Southwest Nigeria.

Review of Relevant Literature Review

Job-hopping

In recent years, job-hopping has intensified as a severe and widespread issue in many firms' human resource departments. Ghiselli (1974), whose work is referenced in Niki (2017), was the first to describe what he called "hobo syndrome"—a notion akin to job-hopping. He said the hobo syndrome is the recurring need to travel from one job to another in different locations. According to Ghiselli (1974), people's inherent impulsiveness rather than structured, rational cognition causes job hopping. Abelson (1993) provided two explanations of what job-hopping is. First, individuals change occupations because they need to try something new or because it's entertaining. The second section relates to the culture of turnover. He asserted that co-workers believe changing employment from one firm to another is appropriate. When employees remain with the same employer for an extended length of time, they may even feel under pressure (Abelson, 1993).

Niki (2017) added to this by stating that while a hobo may seek out a new job for many reasons, such as an itch, they will first determine if their present position or a new alternative one is more advantageous, which is a logical choice. According to Pranaya (2014), job-hopping is described as often shifting employment at the employees' discretion and not as a result of a company's demise. Saleem, et al. (2016) expand the concept of job-hopping by clarifying that it is a practice of moving employment frequently, especially as a method of fast financial gain or professional progress. They partially agree with this logical side of job-hopping. They also propose two variations on job-hopping. The first category relates to a need for novel experiences; changing jobs is a way to do this. Accepting it as the norm is the second factor contributing to a turnover culture (Saleem et al. 2016).

Similar viewpoints were expressed by Naresh and Rathnam (2015), who noted that job-hopping is when individuals often switch employment, move from one position to another, or switch firms. An

effective technique for career growth, salary increases, and increasing responsibilities with each transfer is for workers to move positions with a defined objective or success (Naresh & Rathnam, 2015). Lake, Highhouse & Shrift (2018) further explained job-hopping in terms of advancement and escape driven. Improvement-driven hoppers aim to enhance their career by seeking jobs to propel them toward their ultimate career goal. Progress driven can also be called ambitious ladder climbers because some may use frequent job changes to achieve career advancement through a job offer from another company. Escape-driven job hopper leaves the employer to avoid dissatisfaction with the job or co-workers. The employee quits the organisation to prevent boredom, annoyance, or frustration with the current work environment.

Job-hopping Intentions

Job-hopping intention has emerged recently as an essential construct in human resource management research (Mohammad & Mohsen, 2017). It reflects employees' deliberate tendency to leave their job and the company. It is considered a topic of significant interest in the literature due to its relationship with work-related constructs, such as job satisfaction, employees engagement, and organisational effectiveness (Maier, et al. 2013).

Employees' desire to quit is defined by Mohammad and Mohsen (2017) as the deliberate choice to hunt for new employment chances in other firms. Mohammad & Jahangir (2014) offered various labels for the concept, including tendency to leave, turnover intention, and intent to depart. Steel and Lounsbury (2009) established a more thorough withdrawal procedure that clarifies the processes employees take before making the decision to leave their jobs permanently. Job-hopping intention was split into three cognitive components by Thirapatsakun, et al. (2014): considering quitting the job, intending to look for another employment, and making the decision to leave.

Similar to this, Kim (2014) viewed employees' intentions to quit as a psychological process that includes the following steps: (1) assessing the job, (2) experiencing job dissatisfaction, (3) considering leaving, (4) assessing the cost of leaving, (5) intending to look for alternatives, (6) assessing other options and current job, (7) intending to quit or stay, and (8) making the choice to quit or stay. Karatepe and Shahriari (2014) pointed out that employees' purpose to leave might result in low morale, subpar service delivery, and subpar performance, which is consistent with this research.

Employees' desire to quit the firm or their employment reveals a worker's conscious and purposeful disposition to do so (Maier et al. 2013, 2013). Arshadi and Damiri (2013) added that it is defined as the deliberate choice to hunt for alternative work possibilities in other companies and that this stems from a variety of elements, determinants, and reasons that induce employees to plan to quit. In that specific study, the phrase "faculty member turnover intention" refers to academics' unwillingness to remain in their positions within their academic institutions as well as the factors that influence this choice.

As a result, Thirapatsakun et al. (2014) claimed that engagement and turnover intention are related. According to a study, most employers give this severe behaviour only passing consideration, despite the fact that they must cope with the real turnover that follows logically from the desire to quit (Ramli, et al., 2014). Therefore, studies that focus on the desire to quit may be more appropriate and beneficial than those that focus on actual turnover behaviour. If employers are informed of an employee's plans early enough, they may still be able to convince them to stay with the company. In light of this, it seems reasonable to utilise engagement as the dependent variable in this study while job-hopping intention as the independent variable.

Academics' Engagement

Research, teaching, and community participation are the three main facets of academic engagement in universities (Okpe, et al. 2013; Sulaiman, 2018; Hamidu, 2019). Institutions of higher learning have a long history of doing teaching, research, and service. The amount and quality of these important variables impact a university's performance and ranking, as well as the recognition and promotion of its academic staff (Mushemeza, 2016).

Universities have traditionally focused primarily on teaching. After Alexander von Humboldt's academic revolution in the latter half of the 19th century, scientific research—while still closely related to teaching—became the second most important role of a university. The third function of colleges, community service, only came under debate in the latter half of the 20th century. Globalisation and networking, two aspects of social development, were to blame (Chatterton & Goddard 2000; Oyewole, et al. 2019).

Furthermore, research, teaching, and community service performance were the performance indicators for professors in Nigeria, according to Ologunde, et al. (2013). The three main components of an academic's job description are teaching, research, and community service, according to Fapohunda (2015). These academic positions serve as essential performance metrics for the involvement of academics at most universities worldwide. The requirements and standards for promotion depend on the performance of some or all of these critical academic activities, according to Okpe et al. (2013) and Oyewole et al. (2019). These roles have been confirmed as essential performance metrics for academic engagement at most universities according to Okpe et al. (2013).

Figure 1. Showing Dimension of Academics' Engagement

Generational Diversity

The concept of generation is not particularly new; thus, there are several standard definitions of "generation". A German sociologist initially used the term "generation" in 1928, according to Lyons, Duxbury, and Higgins (2005), as quoted in Shragay and Tziner (2011). According to him, a generation is a group of individuals born and reared within the same historical and social age (Shragay & Tziner, 2011). In other words, different generations are exposed to various socio-political life events while developing. As a result, their expectations, work attitudes, and behaviour at work are typically diverse (Glass, 2007; Shragay & Tziner, 2011). They also usually have distinct beliefs, viewpoints, practises, and worldviews.

According to Lyons and Kuron (2014), a generation is a group of people born in the same "historical and socio-cultural contexts, experienced the same formative experiences, and developed unifying commonalities." The phrase "unifying commonalities" implies contrasts between generational cohorts while simultaneously indicating similarities. According to Keeling's definition from 2003, a generation is a collection of people who were all born during the same period and who are acknowledged as having a generational personality that is influenced by three factors: (1) their perceived age location; (2) their shared views and behaviours; and (3) their considered membership in a typical generation.

Age-based diversity, according to Fajana (2009), describes intergenerational behaviour among older and younger workers that might explain variations in behaviours that have been seen in the workplace. In addition, Kupperschmidt (2000) defined a generation as an identifiable cohort of people who shared crucial historical or social life experiences at critical developmental stages and were born within the same period. Palese, Pantali, and Saiani (2006) assert in their studies that a generation is a group of individuals born at a particular historical period, lived through significant historical events and belonged to the same cultural group.

Given the multiple definitions offered by various academics, a generation may be identified by its birth year and critical life events (Kupperschmidt, 2000; Westerman & Yamamura, 2007). Thus, it may be said that each generation shares the same birth years and that throughout each of those years, historical, cultural, and social experiences, as well as key life events, impact a person's personality within that age. Gursoy, Chi, and Karadag (2013) argued that the current labour force is primarily made up of three generations: (i) Baby Boomers; (ii) Generation X; and (iii) Generation Y (also known as Millennials). The older generations, ventral born between 1925 and 1945, have retired (Maxwell & Broadbridge, 2014; Toossi, 2013; Gursoy, Chi, & Karadag, 2013). The dates indicated by Gursoy, Chi, and Karadag (2013)—the Baby Boomers (1946 to 1964), Generation X (1965 to 1980), and Generation Y (1981 to 2000)—are used in this analysis despite considerable disagreement among scholars over the periods that characterise each generation. Additionally, Generation Z is the term given by numerous academics to the generation that followed the millennials (Johnson, 2013; Nielsen, 2013). According to Johnson (2013), Nielsen (2013), and Srinivasan (2012), the Generation Z cohort was born between 2000 to the present. The Cuspers are one of the different generational cohort groupings, according to Shaw (2013). People born near the generational dividing line are known as cuspers and enjoy the privilege of being a part of two generations.

However, this study adopted the dominant generational cohort in the current labour force, as suggested by Gursoy, Chi, and Karadag (2013), which includes: (i) Generation Y (also known as Millennials). (ii) Generation X and (iii) Baby Boomers. This explanation puts the age limits of these generations like Generation Y (between the ages of 19 to 39), Generation X (between the ages of 39 to 55) and Baby Boomers (between the ages of 55 to 74) as of the year 2020.

Generational Diversity and Job-hopping Intention

Researchers from many fields have examined how generational diversity affects the workplace (Goessling, 2017; Rivers, 2018). According to Jaskyte (2014), an employee may select a specific workplace depending on their requirements, how it aligns with their beliefs, and whether or not it offers perks that are significant to them. Each generational cohort is driven by various things, including chances for advancement, work stability, respect, money security, acclaim, ethical leadership, and fresh challenges (Pierce & Madden, 2005). According to several scholars, job switching is a typical occurrence across generations. The findings of the age group that is more likely to switch employment or have a higher intention to resign are contradictory (Twenge, 2010). As a result, the association between job hopping intention and academic engagement results was adopted, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. framework showing moderating effect of Generational Diversity on job-hopping intent and Academics' Engagement outcomes (Proposed 2023).

This study assumed that the intention to switch jobs and academic engagement are moderated by generational diversity. Boomers are defined as exceptionally hard workers and devoted to their personal and professional goals. This description is based on the idea that employees' attitudes are formed by what they value at work. They rely on their commitment to hard work and to growing their careers. They are driven by power, status, and benefits. Baby Boomers are seen as independent, competitive, and goal-oriented, and they frequently equate their employment status with their sense of self-worth. As a result, they desire to hold positions of power and authority and to be admired and rewarded. These characteristics are more likely to affect their willingness to change jobs (Goessling, Similar to how some experts thought Gen Xers were more inclined to change careers than Baby Boomers, to begin with. (Bova & Kroth, 2001; Jennings, 2000). Gen Xers can grow in their careers, earn money (such as a salary and bonus), improve their marketability, and develop new skills by changing jobs often. According to Jennings' (2000) theory, Gen Xers lack a feeling of loyalty, and businesses cannot gain their allegiance by offering them a decent jobs in an unfavourable labour market. According to Crawford (2011), some Gen Xers motivated by professional progression will take employment quickly to position themselves effectively for moving up the corporate ladder. According to Altierier (2006) and Stueber (2014), Gen Xers are also thought to utilise job-hopping to receive extrinsic benefits right away, improve their marketability, or acquire skills from several employers to increase employment stability. Some workers also thought switching jobs would allow them to advance in their careers and receive salary hikes, mainly when they had the necessary skills and competitiveness (Yusoff & Kian, 2013).

Even though both generations are known for changing occupations often, research shows that Generation Y is more prone than prior generations to do so (Ahmed, Scott-Young, Fein, and Ahmed, 2014). One of Gen Y's generational traits is that they don't mind changing jobs and might not be in a firm

for more than two years (Shaharuddin & Zahari, 2014). Twenge (2010) thoroughly analysed the distinctions between the three generations of workers. The study shows empirical evidence of the Generation Y workforce's greater desire for extrinsic rewards. According to Lyons, Schweitzer and Ng (2015), Generation Y responds better to extrinsic incentives. Extrinsic incentives are material advantages like a wage and perks.

The aim of Generation Y to switch jobs has a variety of causes. For instance, they would look for positions that matched their preferences (having a high level of job flexibility) and tended to leave jobs when they discovered that they did not live up to their expectations (Rivers, 2018). According to Lavoie-Tremblay, Paquet, Duchesne, Santo, Gavranic, Courcy, and Gagnon (2010), Gen Y employees show little commitment to their employers. They are willing to use job-hopping as a means of advancing their careers. Talented members of Generation Y are even prepared to change jobs frequently. They don't care how many businesses or employers must alter as long as such adjustments allow them to achieve their goals (Srinivasan, 2011). Their little loyalty to their employers, the single-minded pursuit of career advancement and better entitlement, and their attitude of "choosing their bosses" (Rivers, 2018) make them more likely to switch jobs (Treuren & Anderson 2010; Lavoie-Tremblay et al. 2010; Wee 2013).

However, Twenge (2010) opined that neither Gen X nor Gen Y individuals would be more inclined to switch employment than those from the preceding generation. Twenge (2010) used one question regarding job-hopping in the Monitoring the Future (MTF) time-lag study. ("I would like to stay in the same job for most of my adult life."). They found a result that is opposite to most cross-sectional findings; that is, Gen X and Gen Y were slightly more likely to agree with this item than the Baby Boomers. However, it is believed that even though the attitude towards leaving the organisations of the three generations is quite similar, there might be a divergence between people's intentions and actual behaviour. When there are better opportunities, Gen X, especially Gen Y, would accept such an offer willingly. Even though there is a lack of consistent views about whether Gen X or Gen Y would be the job-hopping generation, Shaharuddin and Zahari (2014) mentioned that Gen X and Y are labelled as a job-hopping group due to their low sense of loyalty to employers. The work value generational cohorts bring to the workplace is based on their life experiences, historical events, attitudes, and expectations (Kelly & Marie-Anne, 2016). Schaefer (2017) stated that work value is the degree to which employees value their work, demonstrate loyalty and are willing to remain with the organisation.

Theoretical Support

This study adopted Job Embeddedness as its primary theoretical framework. Mitchell and Lee (2001) proposed the hypothesis. The job embeddedness theory (JET) bases one of its central tenets on the idea that employees form bonds with and make sacrifices for their companies. These connections are likened to threads in a web or net where a person may get caught or tethered to the organisation. As seen in

Figure 2.5, these attachments are crucial indicators of how engaged employees will be.

Figure 3 Dimension of Job Embeddedness

Source: Mitchell & Lee (2001)

These attachments are essential predictors of employees' engagement. Hence, this study supports job embeddedness theory in that, in mitigating job-hopping intentions and ensuring academics' engagement, the management of universities must continue to provide sufficient support in terms of grants, conference support, well-furnished offices, and provision of infrastructures for a conducive work environment.

Methodology

The research adopted a survey and descriptive design. The study focused on six (6) universities (two federal, state, and private) based on their year of establishment and top-ranked, as appeared in the Webometrics ranking of Nigerian universities 2019. Both public and private universities were selected to achieve representativeness and generalizability. A sample size of six hundred and twenty (620) was derived using a published table by Gill, Johnson & Clark (2010). The sample was further spread across selected universities using the proportionate allocation formula by Bowler (1996), as cited in Agbionu, Anyalor, and Nwali (2018). Five hundred and forty-five (545) copies of the questionnaire reflecting (87.9%) response rate was returned and used for this analysis. Academics were required to indicate the level of agreement by ticking 5 to 1, where 5= strongly disagree, 4= Disagree, 3= Neutral 2=strongly agree 1 = Agree for each of the respective statements. The data collected was analysed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to determine the impact of one variable on the other. Reliability and fitness were also carried out, while convergent and biased analyses were used to assess construct validity.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

This section presents the frequency distribution results regarding respondents' demographic characteristics, as shown in the following tables.

Table 2: Cross Tabulation of Respondents based on Age Categories

Age of Respondents	Selected Institutions						Total
	UI	OAU	OOU	LASU	CU	BU	
	Uni. 1	Uni. 1	Uni. 3	Uni. 4	Uni. 5	Uni. 6	Freq. %
20 – 38 years	36	34	20	21	11	10	132
	6.6%	6.2%	3.7%	3.9%	2.0%	1.8%	24.2%
39 – 54 years	82	66	24	28	24	25	249
	15.0%	12.1%	4.4%	5.1%	4.4%	4.6%	45.7%
55 – 73 years	35	42	30	25	19	13	164
	6.4%	7.7%	5.5%	4.6%	3.5%	2.4%	30.1%
Total	153	142	74	74	54	48	545
	28.1%	26.1%	13.6%	13.6%	9.9%	8.8%	100.0%

Table 3: Cross Tabulation Based on Present Academic Status

Present Academics' status/ Cadre	Selected Institutions						Total
	UI	OAU	OOU	LASU	CU	BU	
	Uni. 1	Uni. 2	Uni. 3	Uni. 4	Uni. 5	Uni. 6	Freq. %
Professor	16	29	8	15	11	4	83
	2.9%	5.3%	1.5%	2.8%	2.0%	0.7%	15.2
Associate Professor	14	12	3	2	8	7	46
	2.6%	2.2%	0.6%	0.4%	1.5%	1.3%	8.4%
Senior Lecturer	35	20	22	13	9	11	110
	6.4%	3.7%	4.0%	2.4%	1.7%	2.0%	20.0
Lecturer 1	45	32	19	21	7	8	132
	8.3%	5.9%	3.5%	3.9%	1.3%	1.5%	24.2
Lecturer 2	33	39	20	18	9	6	125
	6.1%	7.2%	3.7%	3.3%	1.7%	1.1%	22.9
Assistant Lecturer	10	10	0	5	10	12	47
	1.8%	1.8%	0.0%	0.9%	1.8%	2.2%	8.6%
Graduate Lecturer	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%
Total	153	142	74	74	54	48	545
	28.1%	26.1%	13.6%	13.6%	9.9%	8.8%	100.0%

Table 4. Cross Tabulation Based on Years of Teaching Experience

Years of Teaching Experience	Selected Institutions						Total
	UI	OAU	OOU	LASU	CU	BU	
	Uni. 1	Uni. 1	Uni. 3	Uni. 4	Uni. 5	Uni. 6	Freq. %
0–3 years	0	0	2	0	2	0	4
	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.7%
4-6 years	8	11	1	2	5	3	30
	1.5%	2.0%	0.2%	0.4%	0.9%	0.6%	5.5%
7-9 years	23	39	25	11	13	13	124
	4.2%	7.2%	4.6%	2.0%	2.4%	2.4%	22.8%
10-12 years	45	25	14	22	9	9	124
	8.3%	4.6%	2.6%	4.0%	1.7%	1.7%	22.8%
13-15 years	36	17	4	10	13	10	90
	6.6%	3.1%	0.7%	1.8%	2.4%	1.8%	16.5%
16 years and above	41	50	28	29	12	13	173
	7.5%	9.2%	5.1%	5.3%	2.2%	2.4%	31.7%
Total	153	142	74	74	54	48	545
	28.1%	26.1%	13.6%	13.6%	9.9%	8.8%	100.0%

Measurement Model for Hypothesis

H0: Generational diversity (Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Y) does not moderate the relationship between job-hopping intention and academic engagement .

The Partial Least Square – Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) technique was adopted for data analysis. Smart PLS 3 was used for SEM analysis because this tool can be used for theory testing in the early stages (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011; Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics, 2009; Petter, Straub, & Rai, 2007). PLS also can be used on small sample sizes because this method does not consider distribution assumptions (Astrachan, Patel, & Wanzenried, 2014).

All research variables have been measured using a structured questionnaire with Likert scales. The data collected was analysed using five (5) items to measure generational diversity. The items in the generational diversity scale comprised (Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Y). The responses to all items in each variable were cumulated and analysed, as presented in Figure 4.18. In this research, all items are reflective, and the minimum acceptable value for a factor loading is 0.60 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). All constructs have values higher than 0.60, meaning they have composite reliability. A few items having a factor loading less than 0.6 have been removed, and the results are presented in Figures 4, 5 and 6, respectively.

Evaluation of the Inner Structural Model

The structural model is the inner model in structural equation modelling. The structural model can be measured through path coefficients (R^2) values and significant values. PLS-SEM has been used for path

analysis because PLS do not need any distribution assumptions. The boots strapping method is used to find the significance (Chin, 2010; Sanchez, 2013). The default bootstrapping in PLS is 500 subsamples to gain significant results (Wetzels, Odekerken-Schroder, & Van Oppen, 2009). This study calculated 5000 subsamples in bootstrapping to gain more precise results and the path coefficient values of the three variables. Results showed that staff from the samples had almost the same opinion.

The hypothesis has two exogenous variables (job-hopping intention and generational diversity) and one endogenous variable (academics' engagement). The coefficient of determination/ r-squared, path coefficient (β value) and T-statistic value, effect size (f^2), the predictive relevance of the model, and Goodness-of-Fit (GOF) index were the critical standards for evaluating the structural model as presented in Figures 4.18, 4.19 and 4.20 respectively. Path estimates were calculated using Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE), which is considered tolerant to violations of normality assumptions in most of the psycho-behavioural studies (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Results of structural models and path analysis for the variables have been presented in Table 4.5.5(d) and illustrated in Figures 4, 5 and 6.

Figure 4: Predictive relevance (Path co-efficient) of job-hopping intention, generational diversity and academics' engagement

Figure 5: Path Co-efficient and P-values for job-hopping intention, generational diversity and academics' engagement

Figure 6: Path Co-efficient and T-values for job-hopping intention, generational diversity and academics' engagement

Estimation of Path Coefficients (β) and T-statistics

The path coefficients in the PLS and the standardised β coefficient in the regression analysis were similar. Through the β value, the significance of the hypothesis was tested. The β denoted the expected variation in the dependent construct for a unit variation in the independent construct(s). The β values of every path in the hypothesised model was computed, the greater the β value, the more the substantial effect on the endogenous latent construct. However, the β value had to be verified for its significance level through the T-statistics test. The path co-efficient is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Path Coefficients for Job-hopping Intention, Generational Diversity and Academics Engagement

Variables and Cross Loading	Path Co-efficient (O)	Std. Dev. (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/ STDEV)	P Values
Management supports • Academic staff engagement	0.240	0.05	2.147	0.04
Promotion opportunities • Academic staff engagement	0.162	0.03	2.083	0.04
Remuneration packages • Academic staff engagement	0.190	0.05	2.490	0.03
Perceived job security • Academic staff engagement	0.276	0.08	2.336	0.02
Job-hopping intention • Academic staff engagement	0.300	0.07	2.005	0.04
Generational diversity • Academic staff engagement	0.534	0.08	3.278	0.00
Moderating effect of generational diversity • Academic staff engagement	-0.031	0.07	0.458	0.07
	R Square (R ²)		R Square (R ²) Adjusted	
Job-hopping intention	0.613		0.604	
Generational diversity	0.416		0.388	
Academic staff engagement	0.627		0.619	

The path coefficient of all constructs indicates significant relationships in the analysis at .05. The model showed a statistically significant path coefficient; specifically, an important relationship was found among the variables (job-hopping intention, generational diversity and academic engagement). Hence, all path coefficients were of practical importance since the significance level is below .05. The result also suggested that perceived job security ($\beta = 0.276$, $T\text{value} = 2.336$, $p < 0.05$) and management supports ($\beta = 0.240$, $T\text{value} = 2.147$, $p < 0.05$) have the higher beta values among the constructs that best predict job hopping intention;. In contrast, promotion opportunities had the least effect with $\beta = 0.162$.

Specifically, the path analysis and bootstrapping based on the selected universities were also developed to ascertain and assess the relationship among the variables. To determine the predictive relevance, bootstrapping analysis was conducted. Bootstrapping is a statistical technique used for significant testing of coefficients in formative measurement models. The bootstrapping procedure was used to evaluate the significance of the hypothesis and relationships (Chin, 2010; Sanchez, 2013). This showed the high predictive and explanatory power of the structural models and path analysis for job-hopping intention, generational diversity and academic engagement (see Figure 6).

The value of R^2 explained the variance between endogenous variables (Henseler et al., 2009; Hulland, 1999). According to Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics (2009) and Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt (2013), an R^2 value of 0.75 is considered substantial, an R^2 value of 0.50 is regarded as moderate, and an R^2 value of 0.26 is considered as weak. This study's inner path model for the job-hopping intention (endogenous latent construct) was 0.613. This indicates that the endogenous latent construct's four-factor loading items (management supports, promotion opportunities, perceived remuneration package and perceived job security) substantially explain 61.3% of the variance in the job-hopping intention of the selected universities. This means that 61.3% of the change in the job-hopping purpose was due to four latent constructs, suggesting good explanatory power for the model.

In addition, the inner path model for the generational diversity (endogenous latent construct) was 0.416. This indicates that the three (3) factor loading items (Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Y) substantially explain 41.6% of the variance in the generational diversity of the selected universities. This means that 41.6% of the change in generational diversity was due to three latent constructs in the model, suggesting good explanatory power for the model.

Similarly, the analysis showed that the indicators of exogenous (job-hopping intention and generational diversity) variables collectively explained 62.7% of the variability of academic engagement staff in the selected universities. In sum, the analysis provided evidence that the R^2 value in this study was *moderate*. Even though the moderating effect was insignificant, it can be affirmed that generational diversity and job-hopping intention are predictors of academic staff engagement. By implication, the null hypothesis five (H_{05}), which indicates that the moderating role of generational

diversity does not have a combined and significant effect on job-hopping intention and academic engagement of staff in the selected universities, is hereby accepted.

Model Fit and Goodness of Fit Index

Model fit can be analysed through Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), and Normed Fit Index (NFI) values in PLS under model fit, and factor analysis in PLS algorithm. The minimum acceptable value for SRMR is less than 0.08 (Hu & Bentler, 1998). All values are less than 0.8. In addition, NFI values are related to chi-square values and must be between 0 to 1. The higher values near to 1 constitute a better fit. The higher suggested values are 0.9 (Lohmoller, 2013).

The goodness of fit (GOF) index was used to evaluate model fit (Tenenhaus, Esposito, Chatelin & Lauro, 2005). The goodness of fit index can be obtained by calculating the average geometric mean of commonality and (R²) values ,as shown in Table 6. For this index, values of 0.01, 0.25 and 0.36 are respectively described as weak, medium and strong. After calculations, the GOF index was obtained equal to 0.910 ,which is a strong index indicating the good fit of the model. The CMIN/DF indicates an acceptable fit when the hypothetical model is < 3 (Ferron & Hess, 2007). The decision rule that is adopted to determine the acceptability of the model includes CMIN/df must be < 3; RMSEA/SRMR <0.8; NFI, GFI, CFI must be > 0.90 (Ferron & Hess, 2007; Fornell & Larcker, 2009). The relative Chi-square = 165.25; CFI = .941; NFI = .917; SRMR = .060 as displayed in Table 6. The model fit indices satisfied the critical threshold, which indicated a fitting model.

Table 6: Goodness of Fit and Model Fit Index

The Model Fit Index Calculation		The Goodness of fit (GoF) Model			
Constructs	AVE		Cut-Off Value	Results	Conclusion
	≥0.50				
Management supports	0.618	SRMR	≤ 0.08	0.060	Good Fit
Promotion opportunities	0.783	RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.074	Good Fit
Remuneration packages	0.685	Chi-Square		165.25	Good
Perceived job security	0.647	CMIN/DF	≤ 3.00	2.209	Fit
Job-hopping intention	0.683	NFI	≥ 0.90	0.917	Fit
Generational diversity	0.722	CFI	≥ 0.90	0.941	Good Fit
Academic staff engagement	0.749	GoF	≥ 0.90	0.910	Good Fit
Mean of AVE	0.718				

The measurement model indicated that all the model fit indices were found to be in an acceptable range and above the recommended cut-off level, as suggested by Latan and Ramli, (2013). The SRMR is an index of the average of standardised residuals between the observed and the hypothesised covariance matrices (Chen, 2007). The SRMR is a measure of estimated model fit. When SRMR = <0.08, then the study model has a good fit (Hu & Bentler, 1998). The table shows that this study model's SRMR was 0.060, which revealed that this study model has a good fit. However, the moderating effect of

generational diversity was statistically insignificant. This showed that practitioners' intention to use social media was not determined by social media's ease of use but by its usefulness.

The findings concluded that generational diversity is affected by several factors. Hence, based on the findings, it is recommended that management continue to uphold its diversity policies and practices to increase diversity's benefits.

Discussion

The analysis showed that the indicators of exogenous (job-hopping intention and generational diversity) variables collectively explained 62.7% of the variability of academics' engagement in the selected universities. Even though the indicators of exogenous (job-hopping intention and generational diversity) variables collectively explained 62.7% of the variability of academics' engagement, the moderating effect (-0.031) shows that generational diversity has a weak moderating effect on academics' engagement.

Therefore, it can be affirmed that generational diversity and job-hopping intention are predictors of academic engagement. By implication, the null hypothesis five (H_0), which indicates that the moderating role of generational diversity does not have a combined and significant effect on job-hopping intention and academic engagement in the selected universities, was supported. This tends to explain the uniqueness of individuals within generational cohorts in terms of perceptions, aspirations, and drives. As such, their level of engagement tend to be different (Yuen, 2016; Niki, (2017: Demetria, 2018).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The finding shows that the indicators of exogenous (job-hopping intention and generational diversity) variables collectively explained 62.7% of the variability of academic engagement staff in the selected universities. However, the moderating effects of generational diversity were found not significant.

By implication, generational diversity and job-hopping intention are predictors of academic staff engagement; therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) indicates that the moderating role of generational diversity does not have a combined and significant effect on job-hopping intention and academic engagement of staff in the selected universities was accepted.

The study provided the inclusion of generational diversity as a predictor of academic engagement. Hence, it becomes necessary and imperative for the management of universities to embrace generational diversity and harness the inherent benefits to support the fundamental roles—teaching, research, and community service.

The analysis provided a weak moderating effect of generational diversity; the collective effects of determinants of job-hopping intention and generational diversity on academics' engagement were confirmed significant. Hence the following recommendations were preferred:

- (i) Management should endeavour to promote diversity management by harnessing the inherent benefits of diversity among academics.
- (ii) To foster generational synergy in the workplace, management must comprehend the variations among generational cohorts.

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